

Technical Note -

Age matters in the UK's Brexit referendum

Nouvellet, Pierre¹

Affiliations:

1. Department of Infectious Disease Epidemiology, Faculty of Medicine, Imperial College London, Norfolk Place, London W2 1PG, UK.

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1 Age-structure of constituencies and patterns of votes

In this section, the age structure across constituencies in the United Kingdom is explored, as well as how such population structure relates to the result of the referendum.

1.1 Data

As presented in Figure 2 of the main text, the relationships between age-structure patterns of votes can be highlighted, here we highlight each region in turn.

Figure SI.1.1: Vote patterns and age structure per constituency. As the percentage of younger age-classes (A-B) within a constituency increases, so does the proportion of remain votes. The opposite holds for the older age classes (C-D). Grey dots represent all the constituencies in the UK. For illustration purpose, coloured crosses highlight the constituencies belonging to East, East Midland and London. The grey solid line shows the result of a linear regression including constituencies from all regions

Figure SI.1.2: As Fig. 2 of the main text: vote pattern and age structure per constituency. As the percentage of younger age classes (A-B) within a constituency increases, so does the proportion of remain votes. Grey dots represent all the constituencies in the UK. For illustration purpose, coloured crosses highlight the constituencies belonging to North East, North West and Northern Ireland. The grey solid line shows the result of a linear regression including constituencies from all regions (see below).

Figure SI.1.3: As Fig. SI.1.1 but highlighting the constituencies belonging to Scotland, South East and South West.

Figure SI.1.4: As Fig. SI.1.1 but highlighting the constituencies belonging to Wales, West Midlands and Yorkshire and The Humber.

1.2 Regressions

Methods

To inform the modelling, linear regressions were performed to crudely explore the relationships between age-structure and votes.

In all the regressions performed, the dependent variable was the vote outcomes of constituencies. The independent variable(s) were either one or a combination of:

- The ‘age’ structure, measured as the percentage of eligible voters of a given age class within each constituency (i.e. age-classes were defined as 18- to 29-year-olds, 30- to 49-year-olds, 50- to 69-year-olds and 70+-year-olds).
- The ‘region’, a factor composed of 12 levels corresponding to the 12 regions of the United Kingdom (see Figure 1).
- The ‘country’, a factor composed of 4 levels corresponding to England, Northern Ireland, Scotland and Wales. Note: Northern Ireland, Scotland, and Wales are each composed of a single region bearing the same name while England is composed of 9 regions.

The 3 univariate models, the 3 bivariate models and the 2 bivariate models including an interaction term between the continuous ‘age’ variable and the factorial variable (i.e. either ‘region’ or ‘country’) were evaluated.

As the proportions of each age-class within a constituency are not independent by definition, the process of model evaluation (i.e. the 8 models above) was implemented sequentially considering one single age-class at a time. Therefore, for the purpose of model comparison (using Akaike Information component), 4 runs (i.e. for each age-class) of 8 models were performed.

Results

For all age-classes, the AIC indicated that ‘age’ and ‘region’ had to be included in the model (Tab. SI.1.1 and Tab. SI.1.2). For the 30- to 49-year-olds, and 70+-year-olds, the interaction between ‘age’ and ‘region’ was also preferred (Tab. SI.1.1 and Tab. SI.1.2).

A close inspection of the estimated coefficients (Tab. SI.1.3) indicated that:

- As expected, constituencies with a greater proportion of younger age-class (i.e. 18- to 29-year-olds or 30- to 49-year-olds) were associated with increasing proportion of remain votes. Conversely, constituencies with a greater proportion of older age-class (i.e. 60- to 69-year-olds or 70+-year-olds) were associated with increasing proportion of leave votes.
- Spatial heterogeneity (i.e. per region) unrelated to variation in age-structure was still important, especially with London, Scotland and the South East being relatively more in favour of the remain side given their age-distributions.
- At least for the 30- to 59-year-olds and 70+-year-olds age-classes, the relationship between age and vote was more pronounced in London than in other regions, i.e. relative to the region, in London 30- to 59-year-olds seemed even more pro-remain, and the 70+-year-olds even more pro-leave.

In conclusion, despite the shortfall of such analysis (e.g. correlation between age-classes and the use of simplistic linear regression), it seemed clear that accounting for the regional heterogeneity and the age structure would be necessary in further analyses. As the importance of the interaction term was only highlighted in 2 of the 4 sets of runs, it was felt that it could be ignored – i.e. the relationship between age and vote was therefore assumed the same across regions, relative to the average level (fixed effect) within the

region (different intercept per regions but same slope with the age-related covariate). Such assumption is actually conservative for the analyses which follow, as the regression analyses indicates an even stronger relationship between age and vote in London for 2 age classes (i.e. the 30-59 and the 70+).

Covariate(s) included in model		Univariate			Bivariate			With interaction	
		age	region	country	age region	age country	country region	age region age:region	age country age:region
Age-class	18- to 29	193	32	168	0	116	32	8	120
	30- to 49	188	36	173	22	90	36	0	85
	50- to 69	182	43	180	0	69	43	1	72
	70+	182	40	176	14	105	40	0	107

Table SI.1.1: Delta AIC (i.e. ΔAIC , computed as the difference between the model with highest support and alternative models) for each of 8 models and 4 runs including each of the 4 age classes. Grey highlights indicate the best fitting models.

	Covariates	Degree of freedom	F-stat	p-value
18- to 29	age	1	74	<0.001
	region	11	25	<0.001
30- to 49	age	1	95	<0.001
	region	11	23	<0.001
	age:region	10	4	<0.001
50- to 69	age	1	115	<0.001
	region	11	24	<0.001
70+	age	1	111	<0.001
	region	11	23	<0.001
	age:region	10	3	<0.001

Table SI.1.2: Summary statistics of the best fit models using either each class as a covariate to characterise observed pattern of votes.

18- to 29			30- to 49			50- to 69			70+		
	Coef.	p-val		Coef	p-val		Coef	p-val		Coef	p-val
(Intercept)	0.66	<0.001	(Intercept)	0.82	<0.001	(Intercept)	0.33	<0.001	(Intercept)	0.4	<0.001
age	-0.51	<0.001	age	-0.76	0.006	age	0.77	<0.001	age	0.97	0.002
East Midlands	0.03	0.102	East Midlands	-0.19	0.305	East Midlands	0.02	0.315	East Midlands	0.08	0.366
London	-0.15	<0.001	London	0.69	0.001	London	-0.12	<0.001	London	-0.31	<0.001
North East	0.04	0.148	North East	-0.17	0.696	North East	0.02	0.453	North East	0.1	0.629
North West	-0.01	0.71	North West	-0.25	0.135	North West	-0.02	0.301	North West	0.11	0.216
Northern Ireland	-0.11	0.139	Northern Ireland	-0.12	0.124	Northern Ireland	-0.12	0.125	Northern Ireland	-0.1	0.183
Scotland	-0.18	<0.001	Scotland	-0.33	0.102	Scotland	-0.19	<0.001	Scotland	-0.12	0.27
South East	-0.05	0.001	South East	-0.15	0.202	South East	-0.05	0.001	South East	0.04	0.598
South West	-0.04	0.022	South West	-0.14	0.317	South West	-0.05	0.003	South West	0	0.963
Wales	-0.03	0.105	Wales	-0.51	0.008	Wales	-0.05	0.014	Wales	0.13	0.306
West Midlands	0.04	0.042	West Midlands	-0.44	0.032	West Midlands	0.03	0.083	West Midlands	0.27	0.008
Yorkshire and The Humber	0.02	0.283	Yorkshire and The Humber	-0.37	0.087	Yorkshire and The Humber	0.01	0.668	Yorkshire and The Humber	0.2	0.064
			age:East Midlands	0.63	0.256				age:East Midlands	-0.32	0.54
			age:London	-1.91	<0.001				age:London	1.93	0.001
			age:North East	0.58	0.68				age:North East	-0.4	0.747
			age:North West	0.73	0.161				age:North West	-0.67	0.181
			age:Scotland	0.43	0.489				age:Scotland	-0.34	0.59
			age:South East	0.32	0.368				age:South East	-0.49	0.216
			age:South West	0.27	0.553				age:South West	-0.32	0.471
			age:Wales	1.5	0.017				age:Wales	-0.96	0.167
			age:West Midlands	1.44	0.022				age:West Midlands	-1.38	0.018
			age:Yorkshire and The Humber	1.17	0.081				age:Yorkshire and The Humber	-1.1	0.085

Table SI.1.2: Summary of coefficients (Coef.), and associated p-values, of the best fit models using either each class as a covariate to characterise observed vote patterns. Grey highlights indicate the coefficients for which the p-values are lower than 0.01.

2 Inferring age patterns of vote from spatial heterogeneity

Based on the preliminary analysis above, a model was constructed to formally infer the relationship between age and vote pattern, and further estimate the number of ‘leave’/‘remain’ vote casted by each age-class in each constituency.

2.1 Methods

Let Z_i be the number of leave votes (aggregated across age-classes) in constituency i , and N_i the total number of votes. Both Z_i and N_i were available from (8).

The quantity of interest (i.e. to be estimated) are $X_{i,j}$ and $n_{i,j}$: the number of leave votes and number of eligible voters in age class j in constituency i respectively.

Underlying the process, assume a proportion p_j of voters (at the national level) in age class j votes to leave.

Let’s further assume for simplicity that the participation is constant across age-classes (π). For each constituency i , the proportion ($d_{i,j}$) of the local population in age-class j was retrieved from census data (10), therefore, $n_{i,j} = \pi N_i d_{i,j}$.

If $\{X_{i,j}\}$ were known, the posterior distribution for the age-related proportion of leave votes could be written as:

$$P(\{p_j\}|\{X_{i,j}, n_{i,j}\}) \propto \prod_j \left[\prod_i P(X_{i,j}|p_j, n_{i,j}) P(p_j) \right]$$

with $P(X_{i,j}|p_j, n_{i,j}) \sim \text{Bino}(n_{i,j}, p_j)$.

However $\{X_{i,j}\}$ are unknown, but can be viewed as a hidden state. Therefore data augmentation (22,23) was used to infer the hidden $\{X_{i,j}\}$ states. Formally:

$$\begin{aligned} P(\{p_j, X_{i,j}\}|\{n_{i,j}, Z_i\}) &\propto P(\{Z_i\}|\{X_{i,j}\}) P(\{X_{i,j}\}|\{n_{i,j}, p_j\}) P(n_{i,j}) P(p_j) \\ &\propto \prod_i \left[P(Z_i|\{X_{i,j}\}) \prod_j \left[P(X_{i,j}|n_{i,j}, p_j) P(n_{i,j}) P(p_j) \right] \right]. \end{aligned}$$

As mentioned above $n_{i,j}$ is assumed to be known and an uninformative prior was used for p_j (i.e. a flat prior bounded to $[0,1]$). The $P(Z_i|\{X_{i,j}\})$ term above ensures that the augmented data conform to the aggregated observations of number of leave votes per constituency. Finally given the augmented data, it was trivial to compute the $P(X_{i,j}|n_{i,j}, p_j)$ term.

The joint posterior distribution of $\{p_j, X_{i,j}\}$ was sampled using a Metropolis-Hasting Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) algorithm. After 10^4 burn-in iterations, 10^4 samples of the posterior were obtained (after thinning every 10 iterations). For the augmented data, at each iteration, and sequentially for each constituency, a proportion σ of leave voters were removed from a randomly chosen age-class and replaced into the other age-classes. The exact replacement was drawn from a multinomial distribution with uniform weights. During the burn-in, σ was set to 1% to facilitate quick convergence, and thereafter set to 0.5% to increase mixing and improve the sampling of the posterior.

The procedure allowed to infer the number of leave votes casted by each age-class and constituency ($\{X_{i,j}\}$) and the overall preference (at the national level) of each age-class ($\{p_j\}$). The procedure allowed the spatial heterogeneity to be maintained, and sought to infer the extent to which the observed spatial heterogeneity could be explained by the geographical variations in age-structure. Therefore the modelling framework was consistent with observations made in the crude regression analyses (see SI.1.1-2 and Figure 2).

2.2 Results

The model sampled well the joint posterior distribution (see Fig. SI.2.1 and Fig.SI.2.2). The preferred tendency for younger age-classes to vote to remain, while older age-classes vote to leave, was confirmed (Tab. SI.2.1).

The $\{p_j\}$ estimated reflect a national trend and do not hold at the constituency level. As observed in Fig. 1 of the main text (coloured circles) and the constituency tables of section 4 below, geographical heterogeneity is still present, however the model allows in every constituencies for younger age-classes to be relatively more prone to vote to remain than older age-class relative to the average trend within their constituency.

Figure SI.2.1: Traces of parameters $\{p_j\}$. **A)** to **D)** shows the traces corresponding to age-classes 18- to 29-year-olds, 30- to 49-year-olds, 50- to 69-year-olds and 70+-year-olds respectively.

Figure SI.2.2: Traces of the augmented data $\{X_{i=1,j}\}$: the number of leave voters in $i=1$ corresponding to the ‘Peterborough’ constituency. **A)** to **D)** shows the traces corresponding to age-classes 18- to 29-year-olds, 30- to 49-year-olds, 50- to 69-year-olds and 70+-year-olds respectively.

Age-class	$\{p_j\}$ Median (95% CrI)
18- to 29-year-olds	39.78 (39.65;39.94)
30- to 49-year-olds	40.85 (40.76;40.95)
50- to 69-year-olds	61.45 (61.33;61.55)
70+-year-olds	71.63 (71.45;71.81)

Table SI2.1: Estimated $\{p_j\}$ for each class.

3 Implications of age-structure

In this section, some details are given concerning the methodology to explore the implications of the age structure estimated above.

3.1 Assumptions

In these analyses, voters are assumed to keep their views on whether to leave or remain in the EU in the future. Additionally, the 0-17-age-class is assumed to hold similar views in the future as the views of the 18-29-year-olds in 2016.

3.2 Forecasting future opinion at macro level

In forecasting the future opinion at the national level, only demographic factors are accounted for, i.e. mortality. As mortality increases with age - life table for the UK was recovered from (9) - the national opinion increasingly reflect that of the current younger age-classes.

To infer the influence of ageing, the number of leave voters per age (rather than per age-class) must be known. For simplicity, the pattern of vote within a constituency was assumed the same for all ages within that age-class. From the age-distribution per constituency, the number of participating voters was inferred for each age (as before assuming homogeneous participation across ages). Then, from the posterior distribution of $X_{i,j}$, the distribution in the number of leave voters was inferred per age (not age-class) and constituency in 2016, assuming their distribution within each age of that age-class followed a multinomial distribution with weight informed from the age distribution by constituency.

Then applying yearly and age-specific mortality (averaged between male and female), forecast of the UK age-specific population size in each constituency in future years were produced (Fig. 3A). The mortality was assumed to be the same for leave and remain voters, and therefore forecasted outcomes were readily available.

3.3 Influence of age-eligibility

The analysis was performed in relation to the 2016 vote (no forecast were produced). Relying on the number of leave voters per age obtained above, it was possible to include or exclude certain age groups and thereby evaluate the likely impact of modifying the age-eligibility.

3.4 Life table and weighting of vote

The influence of weighting was evaluated for the 2016 outcome only. The vote of each individual aged i could be weighted by w_i , a function of life expectancy. Again this analysis relied on the number of leave voters per age computed above.

First, a simple and crude weight was evaluated, directly proportional to life expectancy: $w_i = \lambda_i / \lambda_{18}$ where λ_i is the life expectancy (i.e. expected number of year left to live). Note that the weight are relative to that of 18-year-olds. In calculating weighted outcomes, the number of leave/remain votes in each ages were weighted by w_i . The inverse of the weight indicates the factor by which the vote of a person aged i was discounted (see Fig. 3C) in the main text. Therefore, with such weighting scheme, the vote of a person aged 80 was 7 times less important than that of a person aged 18.

As sometimes used in health economics (10, 12), a discount rate, which lower the influence of future years, can be used to emphasise present time. Using a $\alpha=10\%$ discount rate, the referendum outcome would still be reversed with 49.5% (95%CrI [49.50-49.55]%) of weighted votes deciding to leave. Under such a scheme, while the present year is weighted as 1, a year in 10 years time is weighted as $(1-\alpha)^{(10-1)}=0.39$. The adjusted expected life of an 80-year-olds would be 6.1 adjusted-years compared to 10.0 for 18-year-olds, thus the vote of an 80-year-old would count as 6.1/10.0 or 1.6 time less relative to that of an 18-year-old. For comparaison, the National Institut for Health and Care Excellence (NICE) recommend using a 3.5% discount rate (10) when evaluating the impact of health interventions.

The weight used here was relative to life-expectancy due to the long-term nature of the consequence of the vote. Such weighting system could be modified to account for the time-limited implications of a vote. For instance, general elections in the UK are held every five years, therefore the weighting would be relative to such period: the weight would use the minimum of either the life expectancy left or five years. In such example, a weighted system would actually have very little impact as members of the oldest age class considered (90-years-old and older) live on average for more than four years.

4 Discussion of the main assumptions

Some assumptions made in this analyses are unrealistic and therefore the results presented should be interpreted as an illustration to challenge the commonly-perceived view that referendums are the best means to adopt a highly contentious decision with long-term implications. In particular, assuming that the voters' turnout was homogeneous across age-classes, and that the voters' opinions remain stable throughout their lives, are likely unrealistic.

Regarding the first assumption, according to recent surveys (14), the extent of the turnout heterogeneity across ages was perhaps not as important as initially thought, with a relatively high turnout of 64% among 18-24, despites early claims of the contrary (17). Age-specific turnout is intrinsically difficult to estimate; but even if it was known, predicting the future behaviour of those who did not participate would still be challenging, both in terms of whether they would engage in the future, and on which terms. Therefore for the illustrative purpose of this analysis, the participation was assumed homogenous across ages.

The analysis illustrates that for a referendum to uphold its commonly presumed ideal nature as a voting system, one would need to assume that:

- a. Opinions are homogenous across ages and in time, or
- b. If heterogeneous, then the age-distribution must remain stable in time and for future generations, i.e. assuming large concerted shift in opinion with age.

Clearly the first condition (a) was violated in the UK vote. While the alternative (b) is more likely, it is reasonable to concede that personal opinions remain, at least to some extent, stable (see (15,16) for discussion in the political literature), thereby casting doubt on the appropriateness of a referendum. Furthermore, even if (b) was true, changes in the age-distribution of the population (e.g. ageing of baby-boomers) would induce instability in the national prevailing opinion, arguably over timescale of few decades.

5 Augmented proportion of leave vote per constituency

Below the estimated-augmented proportion of leave vote per region, constituency, and age class are presented. Numbers on the right column indicate the median, 95%CrI in bracket, for each age-class separated by ‘/’ (i.e. 18 to 29, 30 to 49, 50 to 69 and 70+).

East region

Peterborough	50.95 (50.4;51.65) / 52.06 (51.7;52.48) / 71.51 (71.06;72.04) / 80.01 (79.3;80.82)
Luton	47.32 (46.79;47.92) / 48.44 (48.07;48.89) / 68.47 (67.96;69.08) / 77.62 (76.82;78.55)
Southend-on-Sea	46.11 (45.46;46.95) / 47.07 (46.7;47.52) / 67.25 (66.84;67.74) / 76.56 (75.98;77.28)
Thurrock	64.19 (63.61;64.84) / 65.2 (64.87;65.57) / 81.26 (80.85;81.72) / 87.45 (86.71;88.15)
Bedford	39.94 (39.29;40.77) / 40.86 (40.47;41.3) / 61.46 (61.03;61.99) / 71.72 (71.05;72.57)
Central Bedfordshire	44.25 (43.76;44.87) / 45.31 (45.01;45.65) / 65.67 (65.35;66.02) / 75.26 (74.74;75.89)
Cambridge	19.21 (18.85;19.61) / 20.21 (19.76;20.83) / 36.92 (36.21;37.94) / 48.2 (47.03;49.74)
East Cambridgeshire	38.88 (37.73;40.16) / 39.03 (38.56;39.56) / 59.64 (59.11;60.22) / 70.11 (69.35;71.05)
Fenland	60.31 (59.48;61.42) / 61.17 (60.65;61.77) / 78.44 (77.99;78.99) / 85.29 (84.67;86.04)
Huntingdonshire	41.81 (41.16;42.62) / 42.74 (42.37;43.17) / 63.27 (62.89;63.72) / 73.25 (72.64;73.99)
South Cambridgeshire	28.07 (27.31;28.9) / 28.47 (28.14;28.86) / 47.87 (47.49;48.29) / 59.3 (58.67;60.04)
Basildon	58.56 (58;59.22) / 59.62 (59.27;60.02) / 77.34 (76.96;77.75) / 84.49 (83.9;85.11)
Braintree	49.09 (48.38;49.96) / 50.04 (49.64;50.48) / 69.81 (69.42;70.28) / 78.64 (78.03;79.38)
Brentwood	46.82 (45.75;48.04) / 47.36 (46.84;48) / 67.51 (66.95;68.16) / 76.76 (76.01;77.72)
Castle Point	61.23 (60.37;62.32) / 62 (61.47;62.64) / 79.03 (78.58;79.55) / 85.72 (85.15;86.41)
Chelmsford	40.62 (40.01;41.4) / 41.57 (41.2;42) / 62.15 (61.75;62.63) / 72.3 (71.7;73.04)
Colchester	42.44 (41.93;43.1) / 43.51 (43.12;43.99) / 64.02 (63.56;64.55) / 73.89 (73.22;74.71)
Epping Forest	50.87 (50.13;51.77) / 51.81 (51.39;52.3) / 71.29 (70.87;71.8) / 79.81 (79.2;80.56)
Harlow	58.5 (57.67;59.53) / 59.47 (58.97;60.05) / 77.24 (76.68;77.92) / 84.44 (83.62;85.46)
Maldon	49.47 (48.09;50.89) / 49.6 (48.97;50.31) / 69.42 (68.93;70) / 78.32 (77.57;79.18)
Rochford	54.37 (53.43;55.55) / 55.09 (54.59;55.7) / 73.91 (73.44;74.46) / 81.85 (81.21;82.64)
Tendring	55.45 (54.67;56.38) / 56.32 (55.83;56.89) / 74.84 (74.49;75.24) / 82.53 (82.1;83.05)
Uttlesford	38.1 (37.04;39.29) / 38.44 (37.95;38.98) / 59.02 (58.54;59.59) / 69.6 (68.84;70.55)
Broxbourne	55.74 (54.91;56.78) / 56.66 (56.18;57.23) / 75.13 (74.61;75.76) / 82.82 (82.09;83.72)
Dacorum	38.86 (38.16;39.72) / 39.7 (39.33;40.17) / 60.32 (59.88;60.85) / 70.73 (70.03;71.59)
Hertsmere	38.88 (37.97;39.95) / 39.51 (39.06;40.04) / 60.12 (59.6;60.79) / 70.57 (69.79;71.54)
North Hertfordshire	33.61 (32.79;34.55) / 34.18 (33.82;34.61) / 54.51 (54.07;55.04) / 65.56 (64.88;66.45)

Three Rivers	39.27 (38.26;40.43) / 39.77 (39.3;40.3) / 60.38 (59.87;60.98) / 70.78 (69.99;71.74)
Watford	40.64 (39.84;41.67) / 41.53 (41.09;42.08) / 62.18 (61.51;63.01) / 72.38 (71.34;73.81)
Breckland	51.19 (50.39;52.2) / 52.07 (51.59;52.65) / 71.49 (71.07;71.98) / 79.94 (79.39;80.6)
Broadland	40.11 (39.2;41.13) / 40.67 (40.22;41.18) / 61.26 (60.85;61.72) / 71.5 (70.95;72.14)
Great Yarmouth	60.12 (59.28;61.18) / 61 (60.43;61.65) / 78.32 (77.86;78.87) / 85.2 (84.59;85.93)
King's Lynn and West Norfolk	53.23 (52.52;54.14) / 54.17 (53.7;54.69) / 73.17 (72.79;73.6) / 81.26 (80.77;81.83)
North Norfolk	42.85 (41.75;44.01) / 43.24 (42.67;43.91) / 63.71 (63.31;64.15) / 73.58 (73.07;74.16)
Norwich	34.15 (33.69;34.69) / 35.29 (34.84;35.9) / 55.76 (55.15;56.63) / 66.71 (65.82;67.86)
South Norfolk	37.74 (36.82;38.72) / 38.25 (37.83;38.74) / 58.83 (58.43;59.25) / 69.4 (68.82;70.07)
Babergh	39.98 (38.85;41.23) / 40.18 (39.65;40.79) / 60.78 (60.31;61.26) / 71.09 (70.47;71.81)
Forest Heath	54.73 (53.77;55.95) / 55.74 (55.02;56.67) / 74.44 (73.72;75.39) / 82.32 (81.31;83.65)
Ipswich	47.51 (46.86;48.34) / 48.57 (48.13;49.09) / 68.57 (68.07;69.17) / 77.67 (76.9;78.64)
Mid Suffolk	41.46 (40.41;42.59) / 41.9 (41.41;42.47) / 62.45 (62.01;62.94) / 72.54 (71.9;73.3)
St Edmundsbury	43.86 (43.02;44.9) / 44.62 (44.14;45.21) / 65.02 (64.53;65.6) / 74.7 (74.05;75.53)
Suffolk Coastal	37.84 (36.92;38.86) / 38.31 (37.86;38.84) / 58.88 (58.5;59.3) / 69.44 (68.9;70.05)
Waveney	48.94 (48.06;50) / 49.71 (49.19;50.32) / 69.51 (69.08;70.02) / 78.35 (77.8;79.02)
St Albans	26.58 (25.8;27.39) / 26.93 (26.61;27.3) / 45.95 (45.55;46.44) / 57.44 (56.78;58.24)
Welwyn Hatfield	42.48 (41.92;43.19) / 43.62 (43.12;44.27) / 64.12 (63.53;64.88) / 74 (73.17;75.11)
East Hertfordshire	38.37 (37.63;39.28) / 39.11 (38.74;39.55) / 59.73 (59.32;60.22) / 70.22 (69.53;71.06)
Stevenage	48.63 (47.77;49.72) / 49.53 (49.02;50.15) / 69.41 (68.84;70.15) / 78.34 (77.47;79.55)

East Midlands region

Derby	46.48 (46;47.01) / 47.57 (47.23;47.98) / 67.7 (67.31;68.17) / 76.93 (76.35;77.63)
Leicester	39.75 (39.39;40.15) / 40.86 (40.54;41.24) / 61.48 (61.05;61.97) / 71.77 (71.08;72.6)
Rutland	37.79 (36.01;39.49) / 36.86 (36.1;37.7) / 57.36 (56.66;58.11) / 68.09 (67.13;69.15)
Nottingham	42.45 (42.11;42.82) / 43.59 (43.21;44.03) / 64.1 (63.64;64.68) / 74 (73.27;74.85)
Amber Valley	47.5 (46.69;48.48) / 48.34 (47.9;48.86) / 68.36 (67.94;68.82) / 77.47 (76.84;78.25)
Bolsover	60.48 (59.55;61.65) / 61.31 (60.74;61.92) / 78.54 (78.03;79.16) / 85.39 (84.64;86.3)
Chesterfield	47.76 (46.9;48.83) / 48.57 (48.06;49.18) / 68.55 (68.06;69.15) / 77.62 (76.93;78.53)
Derbyshire Dales	37.19 (35.94;38.48) / 37 (36.43;37.6) / 57.5 (57.06;57.96) / 68.23 (67.57;68.97)
Erewash	49.25 (48.51;50.21) / 50.16 (49.71;50.7) / 69.91 (69.47;70.47) / 78.71 (78.05;79.55)
High Peak	37.72 (36.76;38.82) / 38.22 (37.72;38.81) / 58.81 (58.33;59.36) / 69.41 (68.6;70.35)
North East Derbyshire	49.54 (48.59;50.69) / 50.21 (49.69;50.81) / 69.94 (69.51;70.46) / 78.72 (78.09;79.49)

South Derbyshire	48.94 (48.08;50.03) / 49.74 (49.28;50.26) / 69.56 (69.08;70.13) / 78.46 (77.68;79.41)
Blaby	47.14 (46.27;48.22) / 47.89 (47.39;48.47) / 67.97 (67.5;68.56) / 77.14 (76.43;78.05)
Charnwood	42.47 (41.97;43.06) / 43.56 (43.13;44.08) / 64.05 (63.61;64.6) / 73.93 (73.26;74.76)
Harborough	37.71 (36.61;38.84) / 37.94 (37.47;38.48) / 58.52 (58.07;59.02) / 69.14 (68.42;70)
Hinckley and Bosworth	47.71 (46.82;48.8) / 48.47 (48.02;49.01) / 68.46 (68.03;68.96) / 77.55 (76.89;78.37)
Melton	45.69 (44.16;47.28) / 45.44 (44.76;46.18) / 65.78 (65.18;66.46) / 75.34 (74.43;76.42)
North West Leicestershire	48.64 (47.76;49.74) / 49.44 (48.95;50.04) / 69.31 (68.83;69.87) / 78.24 (77.52;79.14)
Oadby and Wigston	41.74 (40.64;43.14) / 42.34 (41.64;43.26) / 62.91 (62.26;63.82) / 72.94 (72.04;74.18)
Boston	66.17 (65.12;67.51) / 66.83 (66.22;67.54) / 82.34 (81.76;83.03) / 88.16 (87.38;89.1)
East Lindsey	56.87 (56.04;57.85) / 57.73 (57.2;58.3) / 75.9 (75.56;76.29) / 83.35 (82.89;83.88)
Lincoln	47.24 (46.65;47.93) / 48.5 (47.88;49.28) / 68.5 (67.83;69.38) / 77.65 (76.66;78.94)
North Kesteven	49.24 (48.37;50.31) / 49.99 (49.53;50.5) / 69.77 (69.32;70.25) / 78.58 (77.98;79.3)
South Holland	62.53 (61.61;63.64) / 63.26 (62.74;63.88) / 79.91 (79.45;80.44) / 86.37 (85.79;87.06)
South Kesteven	46.7 (45.89;47.66) / 47.52 (47.1;48.02) / 67.63 (67.25;68.07) / 76.86 (76.28;77.57)
West Lindsey	48.31 (47.28;49.48) / 48.9 (48.36;49.55) / 68.83 (68.4;69.33) / 77.83 (77.18;78.63)
Corby	54.45 (53.51;55.81) / 55.34 (54.77;56.02) / 74.12 (73.48;74.93) / 82.13 (81.03;83.51)
Daventry	45.99 (44.91;47.23) / 46.5 (45.96;47.1) / 66.72 (66.24;67.27) / 76.14 (75.39;77.11)
East Northamptonshire	46.36 (45.33;47.52) / 46.96 (46.46;47.55) / 67.16 (66.66;67.71) / 76.48 (75.74;77.41)
Kettering	49.64 (48.75;50.74) / 50.46 (49.98;51.02) / 70.17 (69.66;70.79) / 78.93 (78.15;79.91)
Northampton	48.23 (47.72;48.86) / 49.33 (48.98;49.72) / 69.22 (68.81;69.72) / 78.21 (77.51;78.99)
South Northamptonshire	41.59 (40.48;42.78) / 41.94 (41.46;42.46) / 62.49 (62.03;63.01) / 72.58 (71.85;73.47)
Wellingborough	50.97 (49.88;52.29) / 51.56 (51.02;52.21) / 71.1 (70.54;71.75) / 79.68 (78.86;80.72)
Ashfield	59.41 (58.71;60.27) / 60.4 (59.96;60.92) / 77.89 (77.47;78.38) / 84.91 (84.28;85.64)
Bassetlaw	56.05 (55.24;57.06) / 56.96 (56.48;57.5) / 75.33 (74.92;75.82) / 82.96 (82.34;83.71)
Broxtowe	42.16 (41.39;43.12) / 43 (42.53;43.62) / 63.53 (63.05;64.12) / 73.46 (72.78;74.34)
Gedling	42.83 (41.96;43.83) / 43.56 (43.1;44.11) / 64.04 (63.59;64.58) / 73.88 (73.21;74.71)
Mansfield	60.62 (59.87;61.54) / 61.58 (61.11;62.13) / 78.73 (78.3;79.27) / 85.55 (84.88;86.34)
Newark and Sherwood	47.58 (46.77;48.6) / 48.4 (47.93;48.96) / 68.39 (67.97;68.9) / 77.49 (76.85;78.29)
Rushcliffe	30.02 (29.16;30.93) / 30.42 (30.01;30.91) / 50.21 (49.78;50.75) / 61.54 (60.87;62.39)

London region

City of London	22.27 (19.85;24.58) / 16.38 (14.99;17.78) / 31.21 (29.17;33.17) / 41.73 (38.19;45.08)
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Barking and Dagenham	54.5 (53.94;55.1) / 55.65 (55.29;56.05) / 74.38 (73.85;74.99) / 82.33 (81.42;83.28)
Barnet	28.03 (27.63;28.53) / 28.9 (28.65;29.22) / 48.42 (48.06;48.87) / 59.87 (59.25;60.59)
Bexley	52.2 (51.71;52.76) / 53.29 (52.97;53.66) / 72.49 (72.14;72.91) / 80.76 (80.21;81.37)
Brent	31.24 (30.82;31.76) / 32.2 (31.92;32.54) / 52.32 (51.87;52.86) / 63.61 (62.81;64.59)
Bromley	37.44 (36.98;38.02) / 38.43 (38.16;38.73) / 59.03 (58.71;59.4) / 69.59 (69.09;70.16)
Camden	18.32 (17.97;18.76) / 19.08 (18.79;19.45) / 35.27 (34.75;35.97) / 46.39 (45.49;47.6)
Croydon	35.28 (34.85;35.79) / 36.28 (36.01;36.58) / 56.8 (56.45;57.2) / 67.66 (67.03;68.37)
Ealing	30.4 (29.98;30.93) / 31.34 (31.08;31.64) / 51.31 (50.9;51.76) / 62.65 (61.94;63.54)
Enfield	34.1 (33.67;34.66) / 35.1 (34.82;35.46) / 55.54 (55.13;56.02) / 66.53 (65.84;67.36)
Greenwich	35.85 (35.41;36.38) / 36.9 (36.61;37.24) / 57.48 (57;58.02) / 68.31 (67.45;69.3)
Hackney	16.51 (16.18;16.89) / 17.23 (17.01;17.53) / 32.47 (31.95;33.14) / 43.41 (42.25;44.87)
Hammersmith and Fulham	22.88 (22.44;23.42) / 23.75 (23.43;24.16) / 41.83 (41.28;42.58) / 53.4 (52.33;54.83)
Haringey	18.14 (17.76;18.63) / 18.82 (18.57;19.12) / 34.87 (34.4;35.48) / 46.03 (45.06;47.24)
Harrow	34.52 (34;35.19) / 35.45 (35.14;35.83) / 55.91 (55.5;56.4) / 66.85 (66.18;67.68)
Havering	59.41 (58.94;59.97) / 60.49 (60.18;60.83) / 77.96 (77.63;78.31) / 84.94 (84.45;85.42)
Hillingdon	46.77 (46.34;47.29) / 47.9 (47.6;48.24) / 67.99 (67.6;68.46) / 77.21 (76.56;77.92)
Hounslow	39.9 (39.43;40.46) / 40.98 (40.68;41.3) / 61.61 (61.16;62.13) / 71.91 (71.09;72.83)
Islington	19.04 (18.73;19.36) / 19.88 (19.6;20.23) / 36.43 (35.9;37.16) / 47.74 (46.68;49.14)
Kensington and Chelsea	22.72 (22.01;23.63) / 23.21 (22.83;23.69) / 41.09 (40.51;41.85) / 52.55 (51.55;53.85)
Kingston upon Thames	29.09 (28.56;29.74) / 30 (29.66;30.42) / 49.73 (49.24;50.39) / 61.14 (60.28;62.23)
Lambeth	16.2 (15.92;16.5) / 16.9 (16.69;17.16) / 31.97 (31.53;32.56) / 42.8 (41.88;44)
Lewisham	22.92 (22.55;23.39) / 23.73 (23.49;24.04) / 41.82 (41.36;42.38) / 53.37 (52.48;54.5)
Merton	28.13 (27.61;28.79) / 28.94 (28.66;29.28) / 48.48 (48.01;49.06) / 59.96 (59.14;61)
Newham	40.34 (39.92;40.75) / 41.5 (41.2;41.84) / 62.13 (61.58;62.77) / 72.47 (71.32;73.67)
Redbridge	36.37 (35.92;36.92) / 37.4 (37.11;37.73) / 57.98 (57.55;58.48) / 68.71 (68.02;69.6)
Richmond upon Thames	21.63 (20.99;22.34) / 21.97 (21.72;22.24) / 39.38 (39.01;39.81) / 50.77 (50.08;51.55)
Southwark	21.01 (20.69;21.36) / 21.84 (21.6;22.13) / 39.22 (38.77;39.82) / 50.71 (49.71;51.97)
Sutton	42.9 (42.31;43.64) / 43.89 (43.58;44.24) / 64.37 (63.96;64.86) / 74.2 (73.53;75)
Tower Hamlets	27.27 (26.94;27.6) / 28.3 (28.03;28.64) / 47.74 (47.12;48.49) / 59.39 (58.13;60.88)
Waltham Forest	32.4 (31.95;32.97) / 33.4 (33.11;33.75) / 53.67 (53.2;54.28) / 64.87 (64;65.91)
Wandsworth	19.07 (18.77;19.41) / 19.81 (19.62;20.05) / 36.35 (35.9;36.89) / 47.61 (46.78;48.63)
Westminster	23.41 (22.93;24.04) / 24.22 (23.91;24.63) / 42.48 (41.91;43.21) / 54.03 (53.02;55.38)

North East region

Hartlepool	58.89 (58.07;59.96) / 59.83 (59.29;60.5) / 77.47 (76.98;78.08) / 84.62 (83.86;85.52)
Middlesbrough	55.31 (54.7;56.02) / 56.42 (55.92;57.04) / 74.94 (74.46;75.52) / 82.71 (81.95;83.61)
Redcar and Cleveland	53.94 (53.23;54.87) / 54.9 (54.42;55.44) / 73.76 (73.34;74.24) / 81.73 (81.14;82.46)
Stockton-on-Tees	50.32 (49.75;51.02) / 51.39 (51.01;51.82) / 70.94 (70.55;71.38) / 79.55 (78.94;80.27)
Darlington	43.78 (42.85;44.88) / 44.43 (43.92;45.03) / 64.85 (64.35;65.44) / 74.58 (73.84;75.5)
County Durham	44.94 (44.56;45.37) / 46.04 (45.77;46.35) / 66.32 (66.06;66.6) / 75.79 (75.36;76.21)
Northumberland	39.71 (39.19;40.34) / 40.69 (40.37;41.08) / 61.28 (60.99;61.58) / 71.53 (71.09;72.03)
Newcastle upon Tyne	39.57 (39.23;39.96) / 40.68 (40.31;41.14) / 61.3 (60.88;61.79) / 71.59 (70.92;72.38)
North Tyneside	40.69 (40.08;41.47) / 41.61 (41.26;42.02) / 62.19 (61.83;62.59) / 72.34 (71.76;73.04)
South Tyneside	49.79 (49.1;50.63) / 50.78 (50.33;51.32) / 70.44 (70.03;70.93) / 79.14 (78.52;79.91)
Sunderland	49.54 (49.05;50.12) / 50.64 (50.29;51.05) / 70.31 (69.98;70.7) / 79.04 (78.52;79.65)
Gateshead	44.71 (44.14;45.43) / 45.73 (45.36;46.18) / 66.06 (65.66;66.52) / 75.58 (74.99;76.29)

North West region

Halton	45.63 (44.9;46.56) / 46.59 (46.12;47.13) / 66.81 (66.36;67.35) / 76.24 (75.47;77.24)
Warrington	42.23 (41.66;42.97) / 43.22 (42.88;43.62) / 63.74 (63.35;64.17) / 73.64 (73.04;74.36)
Blackburn with Darwen	45.74 (45.07;46.55) / 46.78 (46.37;47.29) / 66.99 (66.49;67.58) / 76.42 (75.56;77.46)
Blackpool	55.95 (55.22;56.88) / 56.92 (56.44;57.5) / 75.32 (74.89;75.83) / 82.94 (82.32;83.69)
Cheshire East	37.38 (36.92;37.95) / 38.36 (38.09;38.68) / 58.95 (58.68;59.25) / 69.51 (69.09;69.98)
Cheshire West and Chester	37.49 (37.03;38.03) / 38.47 (38.17;38.81) / 59.06 (58.76;59.4) / 69.61 (69.15;70.14)
Allerdale	45.12 (44.08;46.27) / 45.6 (45.06;46.22) / 65.92 (65.46;66.44) / 75.46 (74.77;76.29)
Barrow-in-Furness	48.22 (47.1;49.61) / 48.75 (48.11;49.54) / 68.69 (68.12;69.41) / 77.73 (76.9;78.82)
Carlisle	47.62 (46.81;48.66) / 48.47 (47.97;49.09) / 68.46 (68;69) / 77.56 (76.87;78.42)
Copeland	49.4 (48.23;50.78) / 49.86 (49.23;50.66) / 69.65 (69.11;70.29) / 78.5 (77.68;79.52)
Eden	39.48 (37.91;41.06) / 39.01 (38.3;39.77) / 59.58 (59.02;60.18) / 70.07 (69.26;71.04)
South Lakeland	32.41 (31.35;33.46) / 32.54 (32.05;33.09) / 52.65 (52.23;53.08) / 63.81 (63.21;64.45)
Burnley	55.91 (55.04;57.03) / 56.83 (56.29;57.51) / 75.26 (74.73;75.92) / 82.93 (82.12;83.93)
Chorley	44.68 (43.86;45.7) / 45.47 (45.02;46) / 65.81 (65.35;66.35) / 75.4 (74.68;76.31)
Fylde	42.62 (41.32;43.91) / 42.57 (42;43.22) / 63.09 (62.61;63.62) / 73.07 (72.44;73.79)
Hyndburn	55.53 (54.65;56.7) / 56.46 (55.88;57.15) / 74.96 (74.37;75.63) / 82.7 (81.86;83.78)
Lancaster	38.96 (38.41;39.67) / 40.02 (39.52;40.65) / 60.62 (60.15;61.22) / 71 (70.3;71.9)

Pendle	51.97 (51.06;53.13) / 52.87 (52.33;53.52) / 72.14 (71.6;72.78) / 80.52 (79.69;81.6)
Preston	43 (42.45;43.64) / 44.14 (43.66;44.76) / 64.59 (64.04;65.28) / 74.43 (73.56;75.53)
Ribble Valley	43.05 (41.59;44.49) / 42.91 (42.3;43.62) / 63.43 (62.91;64.03) / 73.37 (72.58;74.35)
Rossendale	49.24 (48.13;50.62) / 49.85 (49.27;50.54) / 69.65 (69.09;70.3) / 78.56 (77.62;79.73)
South Ribble	46.02 (45.18;47.05) / 46.82 (46.36;47.38) / 67.02 (66.57;67.57) / 76.37 (75.7;77.21)
West Lancashire	42.21 (41.47;43.16) / 43.16 (42.63;43.86) / 63.65 (63.19;64.21) / 73.56 (72.88;74.46)
Wyre	49.68 (48.73;50.75) / 50.37 (49.85;51) / 70.07 (69.65;70.56) / 78.81 (78.27;79.5)
Bolton	46.93 (46.45;47.51) / 48.02 (47.7;48.4) / 68.08 (67.73;68.48) / 77.24 (76.69;77.87)
Bury	42.04 (41.44;42.8) / 43.03 (42.66;43.47) / 63.55 (63.15;64.02) / 73.49 (72.86;74.25)
Manchester	32.33 (32.07;32.6) / 33.34 (33.08;33.64) / 53.61 (53.2;54.09) / 64.81 (64.07;65.63)
Oldham	50.06 (49.53;50.69) / 51.15 (50.79;51.54) / 70.75 (70.36;71.2) / 79.4 (78.79;80.1)
Rochdale	49.04 (48.49;49.72) / 50.12 (49.76;50.54) / 69.89 (69.5;70.33) / 78.72 (78.09;79.44)
Salford	46.85 (46.39;47.41) / 47.97 (47.62;48.38) / 68.05 (67.62;68.56) / 77.24 (76.57;78.02)
Stockport	34.82 (34.32;35.43) / 35.72 (35.42;36.06) / 56.19 (55.87;56.54) / 67.05 (66.55;67.64)
Tameside	49.77 (49.23;50.45) / 50.83 (50.48;51.24) / 70.48 (70.12;70.9) / 79.18 (78.59;79.87)
Trafford	30.64 (30.06;31.35) / 31.39 (31.08;31.74) / 51.36 (50.99;51.8) / 62.63 (62.05;63.33)
Wigan	52.65 (52.18;53.2) / 53.75 (53.44;54.07) / 72.85 (72.55;73.19) / 81.05 (80.54;81.55)
Knowsley	39.34 (38.69;40.18) / 40.28 (39.82;40.86) / 60.88 (60.42;61.42) / 71.23 (70.48;72.2)
Liverpool	31.78 (31.48;32.14) / 32.76 (32.48;33.1) / 52.93 (52.6;53.32) / 64.13 (63.56;64.8)
St. Helens	45.52 (44.88;46.32) / 46.5 (46.1;46.99) / 66.73 (66.35;67.2) / 76.14 (75.55;76.86)
Sefton	34.08 (33.54;34.76) / 34.96 (34.61;35.37) / 55.34 (55.02;55.72) / 66.29 (65.81;66.85)
Wirral	34.82 (34.33;35.42) / 35.75 (35.44;36.13) / 56.2 (55.9;56.54) / 67.07 (66.61;67.62)

Northern Ireland region

Northern Ireland	32.86 (32.63;33.1) / 33.84 (33.68;34.01) / 54.14 (53.95;54.34) / 65.2 (64.85;65.55)
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Scotland region

Clackmannanshire	31.02 (29.57;32.51) / 30.43 (29.77;31.17) / 50.23 (49.57;50.95) / 61.58 (60.46;62.99)
Dumfries and Galloway	32.6 (31.8;33.54) / 33.13 (32.68;33.66) / 53.32 (52.95;53.76) / 64.44 (63.87;65.16)
East Ayrshire	29.32 (28.44;30.34) / 29.75 (29.28;30.33) / 49.4 (48.94;49.94) / 60.81 (60;61.86)
East Lothian	24.18 (23.26;25.14) / 24.17 (23.74;24.67) / 42.37 (41.94;42.87) / 53.83 (53.08;54.74)
East Renfrewshire	16.47 (15.58;17.33) / 16.13 (15.73;16.55) / 30.74 (30.32;31.17) / 41.3 (40.55;42.09)

Eilean Siar	34.75 (32.7;36.76) / 30.62 (29.69;31.48) / 50.48 (49.65;51.28) / 61.73 (60.54;62.96)
Falkirk	31.38 (30.66;32.27) / 32.01 (31.62;32.47) / 52.07 (51.64;52.59) / 63.32 (62.6;64.22)
Fife	29 (28.57;29.54) / 29.85 (29.55;30.19) / 49.53 (49.23;49.87) / 60.89 (60.39;61.5)
Highland	30.76 (30.14;31.48) / 31.49 (31.15;31.9) / 51.44 (51.12;51.81) / 62.71 (62.16;63.39)
Inverclyde	24.81 (23.68;26.02) / 24.69 (24.13;25.39) / 43.04 (42.48;43.65) / 54.52 (53.62;55.6)
Midlothian	26.71 (25.72;27.82) / 26.83 (26.34;27.41) / 45.82 (45.31;46.43) / 57.3 (56.41;58.39)
Moray	37.11 (36.13;38.31) / 37.59 (37.07;38.23) / 58.16 (57.64;58.76) / 68.83 (68.03;69.85)
North Ayrshire	30.12 (29.31;31.09) / 30.63 (30.16;31.21) / 50.45 (50.03;50.96) / 61.78 (61.08;62.66)
Orkney Islands	28.14 (26.11;30.12) / 24.07 (23.03;25.11) / 42.23 (41.31;43.18) / 53.79 (52.34;55.19)
Perth and Kinross	26.2 (25.45;27.06) / 26.59 (26.2;27.08) / 45.52 (45.13;45.96) / 56.99 (56.37;57.74)
Scottish Borders	28.18 (27.22;29.19) / 28.27 (27.82;28.8) / 47.61 (47.2;48.05) / 59.03 (58.39;59.78)
Shetland Islands	32.76 (30.53;34.95) / 31.42 (30.47;32.53) / 51.51 (50.5;52.64) / 62.72 (61.07;64.68)
South Ayrshire	27.76 (26.79;28.78) / 27.86 (27.38;28.39) / 47.11 (46.7;47.6) / 58.56 (57.89;59.3)
South Lanarkshire	25.18 (24.7;25.76) / 25.88 (25.6;26.21) / 44.61 (44.32;44.96) / 56.11 (55.58;56.75)
Stirling	21.65 (21.01;22.57) / 22.27 (21.79;22.99) / 39.78 (39.25;40.46) / 51.2 (50.33;52.45)
Aberdeen City	29.12 (28.73;29.62) / 30.1 (29.74;30.58) / 49.85 (49.39;50.42) / 61.25 (60.49;62.22)
Aberdeenshire	32.7 (32.14;33.38) / 33.53 (33.22;33.89) / 53.78 (53.45;54.15) / 64.89 (64.3;65.59)
Argyll and Bute	26.3 (25.2;27.39) / 26.24 (25.71;26.87) / 45.06 (44.61;45.58) / 56.52 (55.82;57.35)
City of Edinburgh	17.61 (17.37;17.92) / 18.28 (18.08;18.54) / 34.04 (33.76;34.39) / 45.03 (44.52;45.66)
Renfrewshire	23.91 (23.3;24.68) / 24.47 (24.11;24.95) / 42.79 (42.4;43.26) / 54.26 (53.59;55.12)
West Dunbartonshire	26.7 (25.74;27.79) / 26.96 (26.44;27.62) / 46 (45.45;46.65) / 57.51 (56.55;58.72)
West Lothian	30.56 (29.93;31.37) / 31.31 (30.95;31.75) / 51.28 (50.87;51.78) / 62.6 (61.84;63.57)
Angus	31.53 (30.57;32.62) / 31.82 (31.34;32.41) / 51.83 (51.39;52.33) / 63.08 (62.39;63.91)
Dundee City	29.19 (28.67;29.84) / 30.17 (29.68;30.82) / 49.94 (49.4;50.7) / 61.3 (60.48;62.46)
North Lanarkshire	27.12 (26.67;27.66) / 27.93 (27.65;28.26) / 47.2 (46.88;47.58) / 58.68 (58.09;59.41)
East Dunbartonshire	18.14 (17.3;18.97) / 18 (17.62;18.46) / 33.6 (33.21;34.03) / 44.5 (43.82;45.24)
Glasgow City	24.35 (24.09;24.67) / 25.19 (24.97;25.46) / 43.73 (43.43;44.08) / 55.24 (54.71;55.9)

South East region

Medway	54.03 (53.58;54.55) / 55.14 (54.82;55.51) / 73.95 (73.61;74.33) / 81.92 (81.33;82.51)
Bracknell Forest	43.31 (42.57;44.27) / 44.25 (43.84;44.73) / 64.7 (64.18;65.29) / 74.52 (73.65;75.61)
West Berkshire	35.83 (35.1;36.69) / 36.56 (36.2;36.99) / 57.09 (56.7;57.54) / 67.89 (67.24;68.65)

Reading	33.02 (32.53;33.63) / 34.07 (33.71;34.51) / 54.42 (53.85;55.15) / 65.54 (64.58;66.79)
Slough	45.83 (45.1;46.73) / 46.92 (46.52;47.38) / 67.17 (66.54;67.92) / 76.64 (75.47;78.04)
Windsor and Maidenhead	34.08 (33.28;35.02) / 34.63 (34.27;35.04) / 55.01 (54.57;55.49) / 66.01 (65.36;66.79)
Wokingham	31.49 (30.76;32.32) / 32.08 (31.74;32.46) / 52.15 (51.76;52.59) / 63.38 (62.74;64.16)
Milton Keynes	41.13 (40.61;41.77) / 42.17 (41.89;42.49) / 62.74 (62.36;63.16) / 72.87 (72.15;73.68)
Brighton and Hove	23.04 (22.72;23.42) / 23.89 (23.62;24.24) / 42 (41.6;42.52) / 53.53 (52.82;54.41)
Portsmouth	48.77 (48.34;49.26) / 49.92 (49.52;50.38) / 69.72 (69.29;70.27) / 78.6 (77.9;79.42)
Southampton	44.87 (44.48;45.28) / 46.01 (45.62;46.45) / 66.33 (65.86;66.89) / 75.84 (75.12;76.71)
Isle of Wight	47.51 (46.68;48.48) / 48.31 (47.81;48.88) / 68.3 (67.93;68.73) / 77.39 (76.87;78)
Aylesbury Vale	38.68 (38.07;39.42) / 39.61 (39.25;40.03) / 60.22 (59.82;60.67) / 70.65 (70;71.46)
Chiltern	31.97 (30.84;33.09) / 31.88 (31.43;32.36) / 51.91 (51.45;52.39) / 63.13 (62.47;63.83)
South Bucks	37.9 (36.58;39.25) / 37.79 (37.22;38.4) / 58.35 (57.82;58.97) / 68.97 (68.18;69.9)
Wycombe	36.14 (35.49;36.95) / 36.98 (36.63;37.43) / 57.54 (57.11;58.03) / 68.28 (67.64;69.11)
Eastbourne	43.88 (42.95;44.98) / 44.53 (43.99;45.19) / 64.93 (64.43;65.55) / 74.62 (73.99;75.45)
Hastings	42.65 (41.69;43.87) / 43.31 (42.75;44) / 63.82 (63.26;64.47) / 73.72 (72.88;74.8)
Lewes	33.92 (32.83;34.98) / 34.04 (33.54;34.59) / 54.34 (53.89;54.82) / 65.37 (64.76;66.07)
Rother	42.58 (41.43;43.8) / 42.84 (42.25;43.48) / 63.34 (62.91;63.78) / 73.26 (72.72;73.87)
Wealden	39.68 (38.87;40.6) / 40.34 (39.92;40.83) / 60.92 (60.57;61.31) / 71.21 (70.72;71.78)
Basingstoke and Deane	40.22 (39.56;41.06) / 41.13 (40.78;41.52) / 61.72 (61.33;62.2) / 71.97 (71.29;72.75)
East Hampshire	35.7 (34.76;36.69) / 36.15 (35.71;36.67) / 56.62 (56.22;57.07) / 67.45 (66.85;68.19)
Eastleigh	40.09 (39.34;41.06) / 40.9 (40.48;41.4) / 61.5 (61.06;62.01) / 71.74 (71.06;72.59)
Fareham	41.54 (40.7;42.6) / 42.23 (41.77;42.75) / 62.77 (62.34;63.26) / 72.8 (72.21;73.55)
Gosport	52.39 (51.52;53.51) / 53.25 (52.7;53.93) / 72.45 (71.92;73.09) / 80.74 (79.95;81.73)
Hart	35.44 (34.39;36.51) / 35.69 (35.27;36.19) / 56.16 (55.68;56.69) / 67.05 (66.29;67.93)
Havant	49.12 (48.32;50.11) / 49.97 (49.49;50.56) / 69.74 (69.32;70.26) / 78.56 (77.99;79.27)
New Forest	42.41 (41.68;43.28) / 43.23 (42.82;43.72) / 63.72 (63.38;64.11) / 73.59 (73.16;74.11)
Rushmoor	48.35 (47.57;49.35) / 49.35 (48.89;49.92) / 69.25 (68.66;69.97) / 78.27 (77.32;79.47)
Test Valley	38.67 (37.82;39.66) / 39.31 (38.88;39.82) / 59.9 (59.48;60.39) / 70.34 (69.72;71.13)
Winchester	28.59 (27.87;29.47) / 29.21 (28.77;29.77) / 48.76 (48.32;49.33) / 60.16 (59.48;61.06)
Ashford	47.38 (46.62;48.32) / 48.26 (47.82;48.77) / 68.3 (67.85;68.83) / 77.43 (76.76;78.25)
Canterbury	39.11 (38.64;39.69) / 40.23 (39.72;40.91) / 60.83 (60.37;61.46) / 71.15 (70.5;72)
Dartford	54.58 (53.82;55.51) / 55.58 (55.14;56.09) / 74.31 (73.77;74.96) / 82.22 (81.42;83.19)
Dover	48.9 (48.05;49.97) / 49.7 (49.21;50.29) / 69.52 (69.1;70) / 78.39 (77.78;79.14)

Gravesham	54.91 (54.16;55.89) / 55.9 (55.43;56.44) / 74.55 (74.03;75.2) / 82.38 (81.63;83.31)
Maidstone	46.8 (46.15;47.65) / 47.77 (47.39;48.24) / 67.87 (67.45;68.34) / 77.07 (76.45;77.79)
Sevenoaks	41.29 (40.38;42.35) / 41.85 (41.41;42.34) / 62.42 (61.99;62.9) / 72.52 (71.88;73.28)
Shepway	49.08 (48.18;50.17) / 49.83 (49.31;50.44) / 69.63 (69.19;70.16) / 78.48 (77.86;79.22)
Swale	50.65 (49.95;51.53) / 51.63 (51.19;52.13) / 71.14 (70.72;71.64) / 79.71 (79.04;80.51)
Thanet	50.92 (50.18;51.86) / 51.86 (51.38;52.44) / 71.31 (70.9;71.83) / 79.81 (79.24;80.5)
Tonbridge and Malling	43.31 (42.51;44.29) / 44.09 (43.68;44.57) / 64.55 (64.12;65.07) / 74.33 (73.66;75.15)
Tunbridge Wells	33.09 (32.12;34.13) / 33.4 (33.01;33.87) / 53.65 (53.18;54.19) / 64.76 (64.07;65.63)
Cherwell	38.44 (37.71;39.33) / 39.25 (38.86;39.7) / 59.86 (59.43;60.39) / 70.32 (69.64;71.2)
Oxford	22.54 (22.2;22.89) / 23.57 (23.15;24.15) / 41.6 (40.95;42.5) / 53.11 (52.07;54.57)
South Oxfordshire	32.27 (31.47;33.21) / 32.77 (32.4;33.22) / 52.93 (52.53;53.4) / 64.09 (63.46;64.82)
Vale of White Horse	30.93 (30.09;31.87) / 31.38 (31;31.83) / 51.34 (50.91;51.84) / 62.6 (61.95;63.42)
West Oxfordshire	33.7 (32.77;34.66) / 34.12 (33.68;34.61) / 54.42 (53.98;54.95) / 65.49 (64.8;66.34)
Elmbridge	28.87 (27.89;29.85) / 28.92 (28.56;29.25) / 48.42 (48;48.85) / 59.82 (59.17;60.52)
Epsom and Ewell	36.26 (35.23;37.5) / 36.59 (36.11;37.19) / 57.13 (56.59;57.79) / 67.89 (67.03;68.96)
Guildford	32.98 (32.46;33.66) / 33.98 (33.55;34.55) / 54.29 (53.79;54.92) / 65.39 (64.61;66.4)
Mole Valley	33.51 (32.33;34.68) / 33.42 (32.94;33.95) / 53.66 (53.2;54.17) / 64.74 (64.1;65.48)
Reigate and Banstead	38.5 (37.73;39.43) / 39.21 (38.83;39.63) / 59.82 (59.39;60.33) / 70.29 (69.61;71.1)
Runnymede	43.09 (42.39;43.98) / 44.22 (43.64;44.98) / 64.65 (64.02;65.49) / 74.45 (73.55;75.68)
Spelthorne	48.74 (47.86;49.87) / 49.52 (49.06;50.04) / 69.38 (68.89;69.98) / 78.3 (77.58;79.2)
Surrey Heath	38.72 (37.68;39.92) / 39.09 (38.63;39.64) / 59.7 (59.18;60.3) / 70.19 (69.42;71.13)
Tandridge	40.16 (39.06;41.36) / 40.43 (39.92;41) / 61.02 (60.54;61.6) / 71.32 (70.6;72.21)
Waverley	28.82 (27.9;29.75) / 29.02 (28.65;29.45) / 48.55 (48.13;49.01) / 59.93 (59.36;60.62)
Woking	32.86 (31.81;33.96) / 33.02 (32.63;33.49) / 53.21 (52.7;53.8) / 64.38 (63.54;65.37)
Adur	41.64 (40.26;43.04) / 41.54 (40.96;42.19) / 62.11 (61.52;62.79) / 72.24 (71.48;73.12)
Arun	47.9 (47.1;48.85) / 48.73 (48.28;49.26) / 68.68 (68.3;69.12) / 77.68 (77.22;78.24)
Chichester	36.09 (35.18;37.12) / 36.59 (36.09;37.2) / 57.08 (56.67;57.58) / 67.84 (67.28;68.49)
Crawley	48.7 (47.95;49.65) / 49.72 (49.3;50.25) / 69.56 (69;70.25) / 78.52 (77.58;79.65)
Horsham	34.9 (34.05;35.8) / 35.4 (35;35.86) / 55.84 (55.46;56.26) / 66.74 (66.15;67.45)
Mid Sussex	34.18 (33.38;35.08) / 34.73 (34.38;35.14) / 55.12 (54.71;55.58) / 66.1 (65.47;66.84)
Worthing	39.89 (38.9;40.97) / 40.39 (39.92;40.9) / 60.98 (60.49;61.52) / 71.26 (70.64;72.05)

South West region

Bath and North East Somerset	30.5 (30.07;31.04) / 31.49 (31.07;32.03) / 51.45 (51.02;52.02) / 62.73 (62.1;63.54)
Bristol, City of	29.36 (29.08;29.68) / 30.31 (30.06;30.61) / 50.1 (49.75;50.53) / 61.46 (60.9;62.12)
North Somerset	38.22 (37.55;38.99) / 39.02 (38.67;39.44) / 59.62 (59.28;60.02) / 70.09 (69.6;70.66)
South Gloucestershire	40.53 (40.07;41.12) / 41.56 (41.26;41.92) / 62.14 (61.8;62.53) / 72.28 (71.77;72.88)
Plymouth	49.08 (48.65;49.58) / 50.2 (49.84;50.6) / 69.94 (69.58;70.36) / 78.74 (78.21;79.35)
Torbay	49.12 (48.3;50.12) / 49.94 (49.46;50.54) / 69.71 (69.31;70.17) / 78.52 (77.99;79.15)
Bournemouth	43.97 (43.45;44.59) / 45.06 (44.67;45.54) / 65.46 (64.99;66.04) / 75.08 (74.44;75.9)
Poole	45.19 (44.46;46.1) / 46.07 (45.66;46.56) / 66.35 (65.93;66.83) / 75.81 (75.23;76.5)
Swindon	43.59 (43.02;44.27) / 44.62 (44.29;44.99) / 65.04 (64.65;65.5) / 74.76 (74.1;75.53)
Cornwall	42.24 (41.86;42.69) / 43.33 (43.06;43.61) / 63.82 (63.58;64.06) / 73.68 (73.32;74.05)
Isles of Scilly	29.41 (23.95;35.29) / 30.58 (26.57;34.84) / 50.4 (46.76;53.44) / 61.43 (56.31;66.21)
Wiltshire	39.15 (38.76;39.62) / 40.2 (39.94;40.47) / 60.8 (60.55;61.07) / 71.12 (70.72;71.54)
East Devon	38.28 (37.38;39.22) / 38.82 (38.36;39.36) / 59.39 (59;59.8) / 69.88 (69.4;70.4)
Exeter	34.81 (34.36;35.32) / 35.97 (35.45;36.65) / 56.48 (55.87;57.34) / 67.36 (66.45;68.55)
Mid Devon	39.74 (38.57;40.96) / 39.93 (39.4;40.56) / 60.54 (60.04;61.08) / 70.9 (70.18;71.75)
North Devon	42.99 (42;44.12) / 43.5 (42.96;44.15) / 63.98 (63.52;64.51) / 73.82 (73.21;74.57)
South Hams	32.52 (31.33;33.66) / 32.35 (31.8;32.9) / 52.43 (52.02;52.84) / 63.6 (62.99;64.26)
Teignbridge	39.17 (38.27;40.13) / 39.75 (39.29;40.29) / 60.34 (59.96;60.76) / 70.72 (70.18;71.35)
Torridge	46.71 (45.4;48.12) / 46.8 (46.16;47.53) / 66.99 (66.51;67.52) / 76.3 (75.62;77.12)
West Devon	38.99 (37.43;40.44) / 38.31 (37.65;39) / 58.87 (58.35;59.41) / 69.44 (68.69;70.22)
Christchurch	44.24 (42.6;45.75) / 43.33 (42.61;44.08) / 63.81 (63.24;64.43) / 73.66 (73.02;74.34)
East Dorset	41.81 (40.64;43.05) / 42.02 (41.43;42.65) / 62.57 (62.11;63.04) / 72.6 (72.07;73.17)
North Dorset	42.6 (41.3;43.96) / 42.74 (42.13;43.45) / 63.26 (62.75;63.82) / 73.22 (72.51;74.1)
Purbeck	45.35 (43.68;46.99) / 44.8 (44.08;45.61) / 65.18 (64.6;65.81) / 74.82 (74.05;75.72)
West Dorset	35.32 (34.23;36.41) / 35.42 (34.89;36.01) / 55.83 (55.44;56.24) / 66.73 (66.18;67.31)
Weymouth and Portland	47.76 (46.48;49.12) / 48.02 (47.37;48.8) / 68.05 (67.54;68.69) / 77.2 (76.46;78.14)
Cheltenham	32.23 (31.58;33.12) / 33.06 (32.62;33.64) / 53.26 (52.75;53.93) / 64.42 (63.66;65.41)
Cotswold	34.83 (33.69;35.97) / 34.85 (34.35;35.42) / 55.22 (54.77;55.71) / 66.19 (65.53;66.91)
Forest of Dean	44.85 (43.82;46.09) / 45.4 (44.83;46.1) / 65.73 (65.27;66.28) / 75.29 (74.61;76.13)
Gloucester	47.55 (46.87;48.4) / 48.58 (48.13;49.15) / 68.57 (68.07;69.18) / 77.67 (76.91;78.63)
Stroud	32.14 (31.23;33.1) / 32.5 (32.09;32.96) / 52.61 (52.2;53.06) / 63.8 (63.16;64.55)
Tewkesbury	40.06 (38.96;41.27) / 40.4 (39.91;40.96) / 61 (60.52;61.56) / 71.29 (70.6;72.1)
Mendip	35.34 (34.37;36.38) / 35.72 (35.25;36.28) / 56.19 (55.76;56.68) / 67.06 (66.38;67.84)

Sedgemoor	47.88 (47.03;48.93) / 48.68 (48.19;49.25) / 68.63 (68.22;69.12) / 77.67 (77.07;78.41)
South Somerset	43.05 (42.35;43.92) / 43.92 (43.5;44.42) / 64.36 (63.98;64.77) / 74.15 (73.64;74.76)
Taunton Deane	39.45 (38.57;40.49) / 40.11 (39.64;40.67) / 60.7 (60.24;61.23) / 71.04 (70.4;71.85)
West Somerset	45.9 (43.84;47.74) / 44.25 (43.26;45.28) / 64.68 (64.06;65.3) / 74.4 (73.62;75.21)

Wales region

Isle of Anglesey	37.16 (35.83;38.48) / 37.1 (36.47;37.83) / 57.63 (57.08;58.28) / 68.34 (67.59;69.31)
Gwynedd	29.06 (28.4;29.96) / 29.84 (29.31;30.56) / 49.5 (49.02;50.16) / 60.88 (60.16;61.84)
Conwy	39.12 (38.17;40.18) / 39.61 (39.09;40.23) / 60.19 (59.76;60.68) / 70.58 (70.01;71.26)
Denbighshire	40.15 (39.15;41.3) / 40.65 (40.1;41.34) / 61.23 (60.75;61.78) / 71.5 (70.81;72.35)
Flintshire	43.63 (42.96;44.49) / 44.57 (44.16;45.07) / 64.98 (64.58;65.46) / 74.7 (74.07;75.48)
Wrexham	47.07 (46.33;47.98) / 48.01 (47.56;48.55) / 68.07 (67.62;68.62) / 77.24 (76.55;78.08)
Ceredigion	32.04 (31.33;32.99) / 33.07 (32.27;34.11) / 53.2 (52.59;54.05) / 64.37 (63.49;65.61)
Pembrokeshire	42.82 (41.94;43.81) / 43.56 (43.07;44.23) / 64.01 (63.59;64.5) / 73.85 (73.26;74.59)
Carmarthenshire	39.74 (39.09;40.53) / 40.62 (40.21;41.11) / 61.21 (60.85;61.62) / 71.48 (70.93;72.13)
Swansea	39.38 (38.92;39.96) / 40.42 (40.04;40.89) / 61.03 (60.64;61.51) / 71.33 (70.77;72.05)
Neath Port Talbot	44.08 (43.32;45.03) / 44.95 (44.52;45.52) / 65.33 (64.91;65.83) / 74.98 (74.33;75.78)
Bridgend	42.07 (41.32;42.99) / 42.93 (42.5;43.46) / 63.45 (63.02;63.96) / 73.4 (72.73;74.24)
Vale of Glamorgan	36.23 (35.42;37.21) / 36.85 (36.42;37.35) / 57.37 (56.95;57.88) / 68.12 (67.48;68.91)
Cardiff	30.41 (30.09;30.77) / 31.39 (31.1;31.77) / 51.37 (50.99;51.83) / 62.67 (62.05;63.43)
Rhondda Cynon Taf	41.52 (41;42.18) / 42.57 (42.19;43.02) / 63.11 (62.73;63.56) / 73.12 (72.53;73.84)
Caerphilly	45.62 (45.01;46.4) / 46.62 (46.23;47.08) / 66.85 (66.45;67.31) / 76.25 (75.61;77.01)
Blaenau Gwent	50.41 (49.42;51.71) / 51.18 (50.54;51.97) / 70.76 (70.16;71.5) / 79.43 (78.53;80.59)
Torfaen	47.49 (46.63;48.62) / 48.35 (47.78;49.04) / 68.36 (67.84;69.02) / 77.48 (76.69;78.5)
Monmouthshire	35.54 (34.49;36.66) / 35.75 (35.23;36.32) / 56.2 (55.77;56.7) / 67.07 (66.42;67.86)
Newport	44.31 (43.65;45.16) / 45.32 (44.88;45.85) / 65.67 (65.21;66.24) / 75.27 (74.57;76.19)
Powys	38.75 (37.9;39.73) / 39.38 (38.88;39.95) / 59.96 (59.58;60.4) / 70.39 (69.83;71.05)
Merthyr Tydfil	44.68 (43.55;46.11) / 45.28 (44.58;46.2) / 65.64 (64.95;66.51) / 75.28 (74.22;76.63)

West Midlands region

Herefordshire, County of	45.42 (44.76;46.22) / 46.36 (45.96;46.83) / 66.6 (66.26;67.01) / 76.01 (75.5;76.61)
Telford and Wrekin	52.53 (51.95;53.25) / 53.6 (53.21;54.03) / 72.75 (72.34;73.21) / 80.98 (80.32;81.72)

Stoke-on-Trent	59.76 (59.27;60.32) / 60.82 (60.47;61.21) / 78.2 (77.85;78.6) / 85.14 (84.58;85.69)
Shropshire	42.81 (42.31;43.43) / 43.84 (43.51;44.21) / 64.29 (64.01;64.61) / 74.09 (73.67;74.57)
Cannock Chase	58.56 (57.77;59.53) / 59.49 (59.01;60.06) / 77.25 (76.76;77.82) / 84.43 (83.71;85.29)
East Staffordshire	51.72 (50.95;52.69) / 52.64 (52.17;53.18) / 71.97 (71.5;72.54) / 80.35 (79.64;81.22)
Lichfield	45.53 (44.62;46.65) / 46.16 (45.68;46.72) / 66.42 (65.98;66.96) / 75.87 (75.23;76.62)
Newcastle-under-Lyme	51.49 (50.85;52.28) / 52.55 (52.06;53.13) / 71.89 (71.42;72.43) / 80.29 (79.63;81.11)
South Staffordshire	51.89 (51.07;52.9) / 52.76 (52.25;53.36) / 72.03 (71.63;72.53) / 80.39 (79.8;81.11)
Stafford	42.87 (42.12;43.81) / 43.71 (43.27;44.26) / 64.18 (63.76;64.69) / 74.01 (73.39;74.79)
Staffordshire Moorlands	51.66 (50.68;52.81) / 52.34 (51.83;52.93) / 71.71 (71.28;72.21) / 80.13 (79.53;80.87)
Tamworth	57.24 (56.34;58.37) / 58.12 (57.58;58.75) / 76.22 (75.69;76.86) / 83.68 (82.83;84.71)
North Warwickshire	55.2 (54.06;56.53) / 55.76 (55.16;56.46) / 74.42 (73.88;75.02) / 82.25 (81.49;83.2)
Nuneaton and Bedworth	54.92 (54.23;55.82) / 55.92 (55.48;56.42) / 74.56 (74.13;75.07) / 82.37 (81.72;83.15)
Rugby	44.62 (43.72;45.74) / 45.29 (44.83;45.81) / 65.65 (65.15;66.25) / 75.24 (74.53;76.14)
Stratford-on-Avon	37.01 (36.06;38.01) / 37.46 (37.02;37.95) / 58 (57.61;58.45) / 68.67 (68.12;69.28)
Warwick	29.85 (29.29;30.6) / 30.71 (30.31;31.24) / 50.58 (50.09;51.18) / 61.9 (61.17;62.87)
Bromsgrove	41.98 (41;43.11) / 42.51 (42.01;43.11) / 63.05 (62.59;63.59) / 73.05 (72.39;73.86)
Malvern Hills	37.37 (36.12;38.6) / 37.21 (36.62;37.8) / 57.73 (57.27;58.19) / 68.43 (67.8;69.11)
Redditch	51.45 (50.53;52.56) / 52.29 (51.79;52.91) / 71.69 (71.16;72.33) / 80.18 (79.29;81.29)
Worcester	42.75 (42.08;43.62) / 43.82 (43.31;44.45) / 64.3 (63.73;65.02) / 74.15 (73.29;75.3)
Wychavon	43.79 (42.91;44.8) / 44.46 (44;44.98) / 64.87 (64.47;65.33) / 74.57 (74.01;75.24)
Wyre Forest	50.2 (49.27;51.37) / 50.9 (50.4;51.51) / 70.52 (70.06;71.06) / 79.19 (78.57;79.95)
Birmingham	40.68 (40.44;40.95) / 41.75 (41.55;41.95) / 62.33 (62.08;62.6) / 72.45 (72.03;72.87)
Coventry	46.12 (45.77;46.5) / 47.23 (46.9;47.62) / 67.4 (67.01;67.86) / 76.7 (76.12;77.35)
Dudley	56.37 (55.91;56.91) / 57.46 (57.17;57.77) / 75.72 (75.42;76.04) / 83.24 (82.8;83.66)
Sandwell	57.2 (56.76;57.69) / 58.29 (58;58.61) / 76.36 (76.01;76.74) / 83.74 (83.2;84.28)
Solihull	42.94 (42.35;43.64) / 43.91 (43.56;44.34) / 64.37 (64.01;64.78) / 74.16 (73.66;74.77)
Walsall	57.47 (56.99;58.04) / 58.54 (58.21;58.9) / 76.53 (76.2;76.92) / 83.87 (83.37;84.38)
Wolverhampton	51.94 (51.45;52.54) / 53.04 (52.7;53.42) / 72.29 (71.91;72.75) / 80.6 (80.05;81.2)

Yorkshire and The Humber region

Kingston upon Hull, City of	58.67 (58.22;59.15) / 59.75 (59.4;60.13) / 77.43 (77.06;77.84) / 84.58 (83.97;85.21)
East Riding of Yorkshire	46.14 (45.63;46.76) / 47.19 (46.87;47.53) / 67.34 (67.08;67.62) / 76.6 (76.21;77.03)
North East Lincolnshire	59.09 (58.49;59.87) / 60.11 (59.68;60.61) / 77.69 (77.29;78.15) / 84.74 (84.15;85.41)

North Lincolnshire	54.48 (53.83;55.29) / 55.49 (55.08;55.97) / 74.22 (73.85;74.64) / 82.11 (81.54;82.76)
York	30.98 (30.57;31.48) / 31.96 (31.58;32.46) / 52.02 (51.59;52.57) / 63.25 (62.61;64.08)
Craven	38.81 (37.3;40.25) / 38.19 (37.55;38.84) / 58.77 (58.24;59.31) / 69.33 (68.58;70.18)
Hambleton	39.36 (38.22;40.53) / 39.61 (39.08;40.23) / 60.21 (59.76;60.71) / 70.6 (69.95;71.34)
Harrogate	35.11 (34.28;36.02) / 35.65 (35.27;36.1) / 56.11 (55.75;56.51) / 66.98 (66.44;67.61)
Richmondshire	44.58 (43.46;45.94) / 45.3 (44.51;46.31) / 65.65 (64.95;66.57) / 75.28 (74.19;76.61)
Ryedale	41.2 (39.61;42.72) / 40.66 (39.96;41.46) / 61.24 (60.7;61.82) / 71.48 (70.72;72.32)
Scarborough	47.73 (46.79;48.82) / 48.44 (47.88;49.12) / 68.41 (68;68.91) / 77.49 (76.91;78.23)
Selby	46.76 (45.74;47.97) / 47.37 (46.86;47.98) / 67.5 (67.03;68.06) / 76.79 (76.02;77.71)
Barnsley	57.46 (56.94;58.09) / 58.53 (58.19;58.91) / 76.53 (76.2;76.91) / 83.87 (83.35;84.41)
Doncaster	58.31 (57.85;58.86) / 59.39 (59.08;59.74) / 77.16 (76.86;77.48) / 84.34 (83.86;84.81)
Rotherham	56.82 (56.31;57.44) / 57.89 (57.57;58.25) / 76.05 (75.74;76.39) / 83.5 (83.01;84)
Sheffield	40.43 (40.13;40.76) / 41.5 (41.24;41.8) / 62.09 (61.79;62.43) / 72.24 (71.78;72.73)
Bradford	43.45 (43.09;43.89) / 44.55 (44.3;44.82) / 64.98 (64.67;65.3) / 74.69 (74.19;75.23)
Calderdale	43.49 (42.88;44.27) / 44.48 (44.11;44.89) / 64.9 (64.52;65.34) / 74.63 (74.01;75.36)
Kirklees	43.13 (42.75;43.59) / 44.22 (43.96;44.52) / 64.67 (64.37;65) / 74.42 (73.94;74.95)
Leeds	39.26 (39;39.55) / 40.33 (40.11;40.56) / 60.93 (60.67;61.22) / 71.25 (70.82;71.69)
Wakefield	55.27 (54.82;55.78) / 56.36 (56.07;56.7) / 74.89 (74.6;75.2) / 82.62 (82.14;83.08)